

THE EMERGENCE OF CHEMISTRY AND ITS ROLE IN OUR LIFE

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998997272580

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10005702>

Introduction:

Chemistry, often regarded as a central science, has a rich history that dates back thousands of years. It is a branch of science that studies the properties, composition, structure and transformations of matter. This article explores the origins of chemistry and shows its important role in our daily lives.

1. Historical background:

The origins of chemistry can be traced back to ancient civilizations. The Greeks, Egyptians, and Chinese made significant contributions to early chemical knowledge. Alchemy, an ancient philosophical and protoscientific discipline, played a very important role in the development of chemistry. Alchemists tried to understand the essence of matter and discover the secrets of transmutation, finally laying the foundations of modern chemical principles.

2. Scientific revolution:

The scientific revolution of the 17th century brought about a paradigm shift in the study of chemistry. The works of such eminent scientists as Robert Boyle, Antoine Lavoisier, John Dalton laid the foundation of modern chemistry. Boyle's discoveries about the behavior of gases, Lavoisier's pioneering experiments on combustion, and Dalton's atomic theory revolutionized the field and paved the way for further advances.

3. Scientific understanding:

Chemistry provides a fundamental understanding of the properties and behavior of matter. It studies the interactions between atoms, molecules, and compounds, allowing the world to be covered at the microscopic level. This knowledge is essential in various scientific fields, from biology and medicine to environmental sciences and material sciences.

4. Practical applications:

Chemistry plays a very important role in our daily lives, often without us even realizing it. It is very important in many industries such as pharmaceuticals, agriculture, energy and manufacturing. Through chemical processes, scientists develop medicines, design new materials, produce

fertilizers and pesticides, and create new sources of energy. From the food we eat to the products we use, chemistry touches every aspect of our lives.

5. Environmental impact:

Chemistry also plays a significant role in understanding and solving environmental problems. From analyzing and mitigating pollution to studying climate change and implementing sustainable technologies, chemistry contributes to a more environmentally conscious world. For example, advances in green chemistry aim to minimize the environmental impact of chemical processes by developing safer and more efficient methods.

Since time immemorial, humans have consumed plant-based foods rich in sugar, fat, and protein. They knew how to make jewelry from gold and silver 6 thousand years ago. As early as 2000 BC, margimush was used to control agricultural pests in China. In those times, various dyes, zinc and sulfur were prepared from plant and animal organisms in Egypt. All nations have known the process of breeding since ancient times. Each nation had its own alcoholic drink. They made it from grain, honey or grape juice. Vinegar is not only used for food preparation, but also for dyeing. But only special people were involved in chemistry in those times. Ancient Greek scientists dealt with the theoretical issues of chemistry in the 5th-6th centuries BC. They explained that the basis of all existence is four <> - water, air, earth and fire. Later, Aristotle (384-322 BC) theorized that all existence is composed of one basic matter. According to him, the four properties: coldness, heat, moisture and dryness are combined in different proportions with the main matter - water, air, earth and fire. For example, adding heat and moisture to basic matter creates air, adding moisture and air to water, and so on. They can also become each other. For example, when the air is cooled, its heat escapes into water, when water is heated, its moisture escapes and turns into soil, etc. Such an Aristotelian view of the material world prevailed in Europe until the 16th century.

Along with the study of every society, science, the way it passed until its emergence, development, rise and reaching its current position, some stages of this path, the sought-after scientists who lived in them contributed to the creation of this science. contributions, ways of approaching them in the study of phenomena and matter in the environment, and their study remains a very important issue in our modern life. Chemistry also has its own history. Acquaintance with this history, when the science of chemistry began to appear, how this or that chemical phenomena were discovered and they began to take place in people's lives. Studying the history of science is a factor and tool based

on comprehensive, deep and perfect, internally logically connected data of this science. Each era of chemistry had its own historians. But Bertalo, Ladenburg, Jua, Meyer, Marnovnikov, and others did much to create the history of chemistry during the next two or three centuries. In order to better master the science of chemistry, first of all, it is necessary to thoroughly study its most basic structure, that is, the periodic table of atoms, molecules, chemical elements and substances, and their measurement units. It is the smallest particle of atomic-chemical elements that is part of simple and complex substances.¹

Summary:

The origins of chemistry can be traced back to ancient civilizations, and its influence on our lives is enormous. Chemistry not only provides a deeper understanding of the world around us, but also leads to technological advances, improves health, and helps to solve environmental problems. Through continuous research and innovation, chemistry continues to shape our lives, offer solutions to challenges, and pave the way for a brighter future.

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